

ascertain to what extent the values of K for CdCl^+ were vitiated due to hydrolysis in the case of above workers. Moreover, there is some uncertainty regarding the heat of ionisation (ΔH) of $\text{CdCl}^+ = \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Cl}^-$ and of $\text{CdCl}_2 = \text{CdCl}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$. E. L. King⁵, from solubility measurements, has reported -625 cal/mole and $+1725$ cal/mole as the heats of ionisation of CdCl^+ and CdCl_2 respectively. Vanderzee and Dawson Jr.⁶, from e.m.f. measurements, have reported -600 ± 50 cal/mole and -600 ± 250 cal/mole for ΔH of $\text{CdCl}^+ = \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Cl}^-$ and $\text{CdCl}_2 = \text{CdCl}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$ respectively, whereas Harned and Fitzgerald's data on dissociation constant of CdCl^+ give a value of -1070 cal/mole for CdCl^+ . Hence it was thought worthwhile to redetermine the dissociation constants of $\text{CdCl}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Cl}^-$ and $\text{CdCl}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdCl}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$ and also the heats of dissociation of CdCl^+ and CdCl_2 , which forms the basis of this communication.

A cell of the type

has been employed to determine the dissociation constant of both $\text{CdCl}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Cl}^-$ and $\text{CdCl}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdCl}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$ at 5° , 15° , 25° and 35° . Hydrolysis has been eliminated on account of the presence of free hydrogen ions from hydrochloric acid. Since the solubilities of quinhydrone and calomel are very small, there is negligible if any, liquid junction potential between the solutions in the half elements and the solution in the bridge. The bridge is interposed to avoid direct mixing of quinhydrone and mercurous chloride. From the values of the dissociation constants, the heats of ionisation of CdCl^+ and CdCl_2 have been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL

A stock solution was prepared by dissolving cadmium chloride (Renal, Budapest) in dilute hydrochloric acid. The amounts of cadmium and total chloride in the stock solution (of cadmium chloride in hydrochloric acid) were estimated gravimetrically by the oxine⁷ and silver chloride⁸ method respectively. So the stoichiometric concentration of CdCl_2 and HCl in the stock solution could be calculated. Experimental solutions were prepared by adding additional quantities of standard hydrochloric acid, wherever necessary, and then diluting to appropriate volume at the temperature at which the experiment was to be carried out. Double-distilled water was used in the preparation of all the solutions. All concentrations are expressed in gram moles per litre. The preparations of calomel and the setting up of the calomel half cell were similar to those of Hills and Ives⁹ except that silicone treatment was not done. The electrode vessels and bridges were similar to those of Prasad and coworkers¹⁰. The cells were set up in the same way as published in an earlier paper¹¹. The temperature of the thermostat was constant within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Measurements were made

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with a Bajaj Vernier Potentiometer. Duplicate experiments were performed in each case and the duplicates generally agreed within 0.1 mv. In some cases the difference went upto 0.15 mv and in a very few cases upto 0.2 mv. The reported e.m.f. values are the mean of the two e.m.f. values taken in each case. These mean e.m.f. values along with the apparent dissociation constant of CdCl^+ i.e.,

$$K_{A(2)} = \frac{[\text{Cd}^{++}][\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{CdCl}^+]} \text{ and of } \text{CdCl}_2 \text{ i.e., } K_{A(1)} = \frac{[\text{CdCl}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{CdCl}_2]}$$

are recorded in Tables I to VIII. The symbol $[]_T$ represents stoichiometric concentration. Concentrations have been so chosen that ionic strength even in rough calculations did not exceed 0.1.

TABLE I
Temperature—5°

Mixture of CdCl_2 and HCl		E in volt	$[\text{Cd}^{++}]$ $\times 10^3$	$[\text{Cl}^-]$ $\times 10^3$	$[\text{CdCl}^+]$ $\times 10^3$	$\mu \times 10^3$	$K_{A(2)}$ $\times 10^3$	$\log K_{A(2)} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
$[\text{CdCl}_2]_T$	$[\text{HCl}]_T$							
0.0040	0.0020	0.17370	2.65	8.65	1.35	11.30	16.980	$\bar{2}.041$
0.0050	0.0025	0.18355	3.12	10.62	1.88	13.74	17.625	$\bar{2}.040$
0.0060	0.0030	0.19156	3.55	12.55	2.45	16.10	18.185	$\bar{2}.038$
0.0070	0.0035	0.19830	3.94	14.44	3.06	18.38	18.593	$\bar{2}.034$
0.0080	0.0040	0.20410	4.27	16.27	3.73	20.54	18.625	$\bar{2}.023$
0.0090	0.0045	0.20925	4.62	18.12	4.38	22.74	19.113	$\bar{2}.023$
0.0100	0.0050	0.21382	4.93	19.93	5.07	24.86	19.341	$\bar{2}.019$

TABLE II
Temperature—15°

Mixture of CdCl_2 and HCl		E in volt	$[\text{Cd}^{++}]$ $\times 10^3$	$[\text{Cl}^-]$ $\times 10^3$	$[\text{CdCl}^+]$ $\times 10^3$	$\mu \times 10^3$	$K_{A(2)}$ $\times 10^3$	$\log K_{A(2)} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
$[\text{CdCl}_2]_T$	$[\text{HCl}]_T$							
0.0040	0.0020	0.15870	2.63	8.63	1.37	11.26	16.567	$\bar{2}.027$
0.0050	0.0025	0.16890	3.09	10.59	1.91	13.68	17.132	$\bar{2}.024$
0.0060	0.0030	0.17710	3.46	12.46	2.54	15.92	16.973	$\bar{2}.006$
0.0070	0.0035	0.18405	3.82	14.32	3.18	18.14	17.202	$\bar{3}.998$
0.0080	0.0040	0.19015	4.21	16.21	3.79	20.42	18.006	$\bar{2}.005$
0.0090	0.0045	0.19552	4.59	18.09	4.41	22.68	18.828	$\bar{2}.013$
0.0100	0.0050	0.20020	4.84	19.84	5.16	24.68	18.610	$\bar{3}.998$

TABLE III

Temperature—25°

Mixture of CdCl ₂ and HCl		E in volt	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[Cl ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdCl ⁺] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³	K _{A(2)} × 10 ³	log K _{A(2)} — $\frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
[CdCl ₂] _T	[HCl] _T							
0.0040	0.0020	0.14415	2.60	8.60	1.40	11.20	15.971	2.009
0.0050	0.0025	0.15470	3.06	10.56	1.94	13.62	16.657	2.009
0.0060	0.0030	0.16320	3.43	12.43	2.57	15.86	16.590	3.992
0.0070	0.0035	0.17047	3.84	14.34	3.16	18.18	17.426	3.999
0.0080	0.0040	0.17675	4.22	16.22	3.78	20.44	18.108	2.003
0.0090	0.0045	0.18215	4.47	17.97	4.53	22.44	17.732	3.983
0.0100	0.0050	0.18710	4.81	19.81	5.19	24.62	18.360	3.988

TABLE IV

Temperature—35°

Mixture of CdCl ₂ and HCl		E in volt	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[Cl ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdCl ⁺] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³	K _{A(2)} × 10 ³	log K _{A(2)} — $\frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
[CdCl ₂] _T	[HCl] _T							
0.0040	0.0020	0.13025	2.55	8.55	1.45	11.10	15.036	3.979
0.0050	0.0025	0.14108	2.97	10.47	2.03	13.44	15.318	3.970
0.0060	0.0030	0.14992	3.36	12.36	2.64	15.72	15.731	3.965
0.0070	0.0035	0.15735	3.70	14.20	3.30	17.90	15.921	3.967
0.0080	0.0040	0.16380	4.04	16.04	3.96	20.08	16.364	3.956
0.0090	0.0045	0.16946	4.33	17.83	4.67	22.16	16.532	3.949
0.0100	0.0050	0.17457	4.66	19.66	5.34	24.32	17.157	3.954

TABLE V

Temperature—5°

Mixture of CdCl ₂ and HCl		E in volt	[Cl ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdCl ⁺] × 10 ³	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[CdCl ₂] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³	K _{A(1)} × 10 ²	log K _{A(1)} — $\frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
[CdCl ₂] _T	[HCl] _T								
0.0200	0.0110	0.24321	36.15	12.07	7.04	0.89	43.19	49.026	1.521
0.0220	0.0110	0.24725	39.25	13.54	7.36	1.10	46.61	48.323	1.509
0.0240	0.0120	0.25099	42.21	15.09	7.66	1.25	50.07	51.119	1.529
0.0260	0.0130	0.25435	45.37	16.55	7.91	1.54	53.28	48.758	1.503
0.0280	0.0140	0.25755	48.49	18.15	8.17	1.68	56.66	52.388	1.530
0.0300	0.0150	0.26045	51.41	19.63	8.39	1.98	59.80	50.969	1.514

TABLE VI

Temperature—15°

Mixture of CdCl ₂ and HCl		E in volt	[Cl ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdCl ⁺] × 10 ³	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[CdCl ₂] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³	K _{A(1)}} × 10 ²	log K _{A(1)}} - $\frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
[CdCl ₂] _T	[HCl] _T								
0.0200	0.0100	0.23066	36.02	12.18	6.92	0.90	42.94	47.747	1.516
0.0220	0.0110	0.23485	39.12	13.65	7.24	1.11	46.36	48.107	1.505
0.0240	0.0120	0.23870	42.23	15.17	7.53	1.30	49.76	49.279	1.510
0.0260	0.0130	0.24223	45.28	16.69	7.80	1.51	53.08	50.381	1.515
0.0280	0.0140	0.24548	48.26 *	18.18	8.04	1.78	56.30	49.290	1.501
0.0300	0.0150	0.24852	51.24	19.71	8.27	2.02	59.50	49.997	1.503

TABLE VII

Temperature—25°

Mixture of CdCl ₂ and HCl		E in volt	[Cl ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdCl ⁺] × 10 ³	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[CdCl ₂] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³	K _{A(1)}} × 10 ²	log K _{A(1)}} - $\frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
[CdCl ₂] _T	[HCl] _T								
0.0200	0.0100	0.21845	35.75	12.13	6.81	1.06	42.56	40.910	1.438
0.0220	0.0110	0.22280	38.86	13.62	7.12	1.26	45.98	42.006	1.443
0.0240	0.0120	0.22674	41.87	15.08	7.40	1.52	49.27	41.539	1.433
0.0260	0.0130	0.23040	44.92	16.60	7.66	1.74	52.58	42.855	1.442
0.0280	0.0140	0.23378	47.92	18.12	7.90	1.98	55.82	43.854	1.447
0.0300	0.0150	0.23688	50.78	19.57	8.10	2.33	58.89	42.651	1.431

TABLE VIII

Temperature—35°

Mixture of CdCl ₂ and HCl		E in volt	[Cl ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdCl ⁺] × 10 ³	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[CdCl ₂] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³	K _{A(1)}} × 10 ²	log K _{A(1)}} - $\frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
[CdCl ₂] _T	[HCl] _T								
0.0200	0.0100	0.20670	35.13	12.33	6.40	1.27	41.53	34.106	1.357
0.0220	0.0110	0.21113	38.09	13.78	6.66	1.56	44.75	33.646	1.346
0.0240	0.0120	0.21520	41.05	15.26	6.90	1.84	47.95	34.045	1.346
0.0260	0.0130	0.21896	44.01	16.67	7.12	2.11	51.18	34.979	1.352
0.0280	0.0140	0.22235	46.75	18.16	7.30	2.54	54.05	33.424	1.328
0.0300	0.0150	0.22560	49.65	19.68	7.49	2.83	57.14	34.527	1.338

DISCUSSION

The e.m.f. of the cell, $\text{Hg} \left| \begin{array}{c} \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2 \\ \text{CdCl}_2(c_2) \end{array} \right| \begin{array}{c} \text{HCl}(c_1) \\ \text{CdCl}_2(c_2) \end{array} \left| \begin{array}{c} \text{HCl}(c_1) \\ \text{CdCl}_2(c_2) \end{array} \right| \text{Q.H.} \left| \text{Pt} \right.$

is given by;
$$E = E_0 + \frac{2.30259RT}{F} \log[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]f_{\text{H}^+}f_{\text{Cl}^-} \quad (1)$$

The activity coefficient product is given by the expression;

$$-\log f_{\text{H}^+}f_{\text{Cl}^-} = \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - B\mu \quad (2)$$

Here 'A' is the constant of Debye-Hückel equation and 'B' is found from the study of the cell reported earlier¹¹. The values of 'A' and 'B' at various temperatures are given below :

	5°	15°	25°	35°
A	0.4921	0.5002	0.5092	0.5190
B	0.4440	0.4664	0.4750	0.4684

Assuming that the first stage of dissociation; $\text{CdCl}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdCl}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$ is complete in very dilute solutions; the only ions present in these solutions can be Cd^{++} , CdCl^+ , Cl^- and H^+ and the ionic strength of the solution will be given by the following equation :

$$\mu = 2[\text{Cd}^{++}] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{CdCl}^+] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{Cl}^-] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{H}^+] \quad (3)$$

So far $[\text{H}^+]$ is concerned, it is evidently equal to $[\text{HCl}]_T$. For finding the value of other concentration terms, an arbitrary value is given to μ . The corresponding value of $f_{\text{H}^+}f_{\text{Cl}^-}$, is calculated from equation (2), thereafter that of $[\text{Cl}^-]$ from equation (1), that of $[\text{CdCl}^+]$ from the relationship, $[\text{Cl}^-] + [\text{CdCl}^+] = 2[\text{CdCl}_2]_T + [\text{HCl}]_T$ and that of $[\text{Cd}^{++}]$ from the relationship $[\text{CdCl}_2]_T = [\text{Cd}^{++}] + [\text{CdCl}^+]$. The last two relationships are based respectively on the facts (i) chlorine comes only from CdCl_2 and HCl and is present only as Cl^- and CdCl^+ . (ii) CdCl_2 gives rise to only two cadmium bearing units i.e., Cd^{++} and CdCl^+ . With the values of $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{Cl}^-]$, $[\text{CdCl}^+]$ and $[\text{Cd}^{++}]$ thus found, a new value of μ is obtained. This process is repeated till μ becomes constant within experimental error. These final values of $[\text{Cl}^-]$, $[\text{CdCl}^+]$, and $[\text{Cd}^{++}]$ corresponding to the constant value of μ represent the correct values of concentrations and they are given in the tables.

The dissociation constant (K_2) of CdCl^+ is given by

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{Cd}^{++}][\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{CdCl}^+]} \times \frac{f_{\text{Cd}^{++}}f_{\text{Cl}^-}}{f_{\text{CdCl}^+}} = K_{A(2)} \frac{f_{\text{Cd}^{++}}f_{\text{Cl}^-}}{f_{\text{CdCl}^+}}$$

Applying the equation, $-\log f_i = \frac{AZi^2\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - B_i\mu$,

we get,

$$\log K_{A(2)} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_2 - \beta\mu \quad (4)$$

The value of $K_{A(2)}$ is next calculated from the values of $[Cd^{++}]$, $[Cl^-]$ and $[CdCl^+]$ determined, as explained earlier. The left hand side of equation (4) is plotted against μ and the value of $\log K_2$ is obtained from the intercept of the straight line corresponding to $\mu = 0$, drawn in such a manner that when all the adjacent points are joined, equal areas lie above and below the line and the line passes through the maximum number of points. The value of β is calculated from the slope of the straight line. The values of K_2 and β at various temperatures are given below :

	5°	15°	25°	35°
$K_2 \times 10^2$	1.161	1.097	1.069	0.998
β	1.84	1.68	1.76	2.16

It may be pointed out that the above scheme works only up to 0.01M cadmium chloride solutions. Tables I to IV cover this range. When the concentration of $CdCl_2$ exceeds 0.01, it has been presumed that the scheme of dissociation is as given below :

Even when undissociated $CdCl_2$ is present, the only ions present in the solution are Cl^- , Cd^{++} , $CdCl^+$ and H^+ . From the principle of electroneutrality it follows that, $[Cl^-] = 2[Cd^{++}] + [CdCl^+] + [H^+]$. Since $[H^+] = [HCl]_T$, so

$$[Cl^-] - [HCl]_T = 2[Cd^{++}] + [CdCl^+] \quad (5)$$

Substituting the value of $[Cd^{++}] = \frac{K_{A(2)} \times [CdCl^+]}{[Cl^-]}$ in (5) we get,

$$[Cl^-] - [HCl]_T = \frac{2K_{A(2)} \times [CdCl^+]}{[Cl^-]} + [CdCl^+] \quad (6)$$

To determine the values of $[Cd^{++}]$, $[Cl^-]$ and $[CdCl^+]$, an arbitrary value is given to μ and the corresponding values of $f_{H^+}f_{Cl^-}$ and $[Cl^-]$ are found as explained earlier and that of $K_{A(2)}$ is found from equation (4). Substituting these values in equation (6) we get the corresponding value of $[CdCl^+]$ and then from equation (5) we get the corresponding value of $[Cd^{++}]$. With these values a new value of μ is calculated from equation (3). The process is repeated till μ is constant up to the 5th place of decimal. The values of $[Cd^{++}]$, $[CdCl^+]$, $[Cl^-]$ at this constant value of μ represent correct concentrations of the ions. The value of $[CdCl_2]$ is then found from the equation, $[CdCl_2]_T = [Cd^{++}] + [CdCl^+] + [CdCl_2]$. The necessary values are given in Tables V to VIII.

Now $K_1 = K_{A(1)} \times f_{Cd^{++}}f_{Cl^-}$, because the activity coefficient of undissociated cadmium chloride can be taken to be unity. So we can write :

$$\log K_{A(1)} - \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_1 - b\mu \quad (7)$$

Now $K_{A(1)}$ is found from the values of $[\text{CdCl}^+]$, $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and $[\text{CdCl}_2]$ determined as explained earlier. Left hand side of the equation (7) is plotted against μ taking the same care as in the case of determination of $\log K_2$. This plot gives the value of 'b' and $\log K_1$. The values of K_1 at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° are found to be 0.35, 0.34, 0.29 and 0.24 respectively.

Heat content change due to ionisation : The value of ΔH for the reaction $\text{CdCl}^+ = \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Cl}^-$ has been calculated by plotting $\log K_2$ against $1/T$ and it comes out to be -800 ± 100 cal./mole. The plot of $\log K_1$ against $1/T$ similarly gives the value of ΔH for the reaction $\text{CdCl}_2 = \text{CdCl}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$ and ΔH comes out to be -1450 ± 100 cal./mole. Our value of ΔH for $\text{CdCl}^+ = \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Cl}^-$ is higher than that of Vanderjee and Dawson Jr.⁶ and lower than that that of Harned and Fitzgerald² and is more or less equal to the mean (-830 cal.) of the two. The values of ΔH for $\text{CdCl}_2 = \text{CdCl}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$ calculated from the work of Vanderzee and Dawson Jr.⁶ based on their data at ionic strengths ranging from 0.5 to 3.0 comes to -600 ± 250 whereas King's⁵ value based on the solubility measurements at constant ionic strength of 3.0 comes to $+1725$ cal./mole. Our work confirms Vanderzee and Dawson's finding that the reaction $\text{CdCl}_2 = \text{CdCl}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$ is exothermic. Our values of ΔH for both the above reactions should be more reliable since we have worked at ionic strengths where Debye-Hückel

modified equation, $-\log f_i = \frac{AZi^2\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - Bi\mu$ is applicable and where extrapolation to zero

ionic strength is justified.

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